

Association of Body Mass Index with Serum Total Cholesterol, HDL And LDL Cholesterol in Type-2 Diabetes MellitusMarshnil RW¹, Ganesh G²¹Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Government Thoothukudi Medical College, Thoothukudi, Tamil Nadu, India²Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Government Stanley Medical College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: There is increased risk of developing Diabetes with progressive rise in Body mass Index. Dyslipidemia in Diabetes is one of the major reasons for sudden cardiac death in diabetic patients. Life style modifications along with good dietary habits are extremely essential to prevent Obesity and development of dyslipidemia in Diabetes.

Aim: This study aims to look for the association between Body mass Index and dyslipidemia in patients with type-2- Diabetes Mellitus.

Materials and Methods: This Cross- sectional study included 100 patients with type-2 Diabetes mellitus. Blood samples were analysed for assessing Fasting and Post Prandial blood sugar, serum Total Cholesterol, serum HDL and serum LDL Cholesterol levels. Body mass Index was calculated from height in meters and weight in kilograms. Statistical analysis was done using Chi square test and pearson's correlation. Statistical significance with p-value less than 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results: Our results displayed a significant positive association between serum Total Cholesterol, serum LDL Cholesterol levels and BMI (Body Mass Index), with ($r=0.40$ and $r=0.17$) respectively; and a significant negative correlation between serum HDL Cholesterol levels and BMI (Body Mass Index), with ($r=-0.19$) in diabetic patients with increase in BMI (Body Mass Index).

Conclusion: Diabetic patients with increased Body mass Index are more prone to develop dyslipidemia, which is the most important risk factor for developing atherosclerosis and coronary artery disease. Thus, from our study, we recommend appropriate life style changes in patients with type-2 Diabetes, which will definitely lower the risk of development of dyslipidemia and cardiovascular side effects in Diabetes.

Keywords: Body mass Index, dyslipidemia, serum Total Cholesterol, serum HDL Cholesterol, serum LDL Cholesterol, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

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Introduction

Diabetes Mellitus has become a major world health problem- mostly in developing countries like India. Diabetes is a world-wide epidemic, because it is often associated with increased rates of obesity. Along with obesity, dyslipidemia is also much more common in patients with Diabetes. Dyslipidemia in Diabetes is mostly characterized by increased triglycerides with low High-density lipoprotein and increased Low density lipoprotein levels. They form the component of metabolic syndrome in patients with Diabetes [1]. Epidemiological studies have shown that obese individuals with (BMI > 35) have higher probability of developing type-2 Diabetes. This is mostly due to genetic factors, with associated sedentary life style in these individuals [2].

Increased body fat is associated with Insulin resistance and increased prevalence of Diabetes in Indian population [3]. In patients with Diabetes, LDL Cholesterol is the major lipid profile marker in predicting cardiovascular risk, and is the major therapeutic target for lowering cardiovascular risk [4]. Also, various studies have demonstrated that, increased HDL Cholesterol levels are associated with decreased risk of cardiovascular side effects in patients with Diabetes mellitus [5]. Early diagnosis and proper interventions to normalise circulating lipid levels have shown to reduce cardiovascular complications and mortality among patients with Diabetes [6]. Thus, the aim of this study is to find out the association between Body mass Index and

serum Lipid profile in type-2 Diabetic patients- especially in South Indian Population.

Materials and Methods

Study design: The study was a cross-sectional study that was conducted in a tertiary care medical college and hospital of South Tamilnadu. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional ethical committee of the hospital (SMIMS/IHEC/2012/A1). A total of 100 patients with type-2 Diabetes aged between 40-70 years were included in the study, after considering suitable inclusion and exclusion criteria. Informed written consent was obtained from all the study participants.

Study Procedure: Fasting blood samples were collected from the study participants after 8 to 12 hours of fasting, and the sample was used for assessing Fasting blood sugar, serum Total Cholesterol, serum HDL and serum LDL Cholesterol levels. Serum LDL Cholesterol was determined by the Friedewald formula, for which serum Triglyceride levels were also determined. Friedewald formula: LDL cholesterol = Total cholesterol - (HDL cholesterol + TGL/5). Post prandial blood sample was used for post prandial blood sugar analysis. Lipid profile and blood sugar

was estimated using fully automated clinical chemistry analyser in the central biochemistry laboratory.

Body mass Index was calculated using the formula, weight (kg)/height (m²). Body weight was measured using calibrated weighing scale in standing posture, and was measured in kilograms (kgs).

Height was measured using a wall mounted stadiometer, and was adjusted to the nearest 0.5 cm, and the patient was asked to stand in upright posture, with their back to the height rule. Patients with BMI >25 was considered as over-weight and with BMI >30 was considered as obese.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical data was analysed using SPSS software, version 21.0. Results were expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Statistically significant association was determined by using Chi square test.

P value less than 0.05 was considered as a level of significance. To find out, whether there was any significant correlation between two variables, Pearson's correlation was used.

Results

Table 1: Comparison between Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum HDL Cholesterol, Serum LDL Cholesterol and BMI in type-2 Diabetic patients

	BMI<25 (N= 4)	BMI>25 (N= 96)	BMI>30 (N= 57)	P-Value
Serum Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	215.5± 49.95	275.67± 56.35	295.66± 52.74	0.000**
Serum HDL Cholesterol (mg/dl)	50.25± 6.98	40.86± 12.42	38.19± 12.18	0.04*
Serum LDL Cholesterol (mg/dl)	136.25± 46.57	169.98± 48.86	177.68± 51.79	0.08

** - Highly Significant (p < 0.001), * - Significant (p < 0.05)

Table -1 shows that, the mean values of serum Total Cholesterol was higher in type-2 Diabetic patients with BMI >25, and in obese Diabetic patients with BMI >30, and the difference was found to be statistically significant (p value<0.001).

The mean serum HDL Cholesterol levels were found to be lower in type-2 Diabetic patients with BMI >25, and in obese diabetic patients with BMI >30, and this difference was also found to be statistically significant (p value<0.001).

The mean values of serum LDL Cholesterol did not show any statistical significance, with increase in

BMI in type-2 Diabetic patients. Table - 2 shows that, there was a significant positive correlation between BMI and serum Total Cholesterol and serum LDL Cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients; (r= 0.40) and (r=0.17) respectively. This has also been represented in Figures-1 and 3 in the form of scatter diagrams. Table - 2 also shows that, there was a significant negative correlation between BMI and serum HDL Cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients; (r=-0.19). Figure-2 shows a scatter diagram indicating the negative correlation between BMI and serum HDL Cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients.

Table 2: Correlation between Serum Total Cholesterol, Serum HDL Cholesterol, Serum LDL Cholesterol and BMI in type-2 Diabetic patients

		Serum Total Cholesterol	Serum HDL Cholesterol	Serum LDL Cholesterol
Body Mass Index	Pearson correlation	0.40**	-0.19**	0.17**
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00
	N	100	100	100

** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Figure 1: Scatter diagram showing positive Correlation between BMI and Serum Total Cholesterol in type-2 Diabetic patients

Figure 2: Scatter diagram showing negative Correlation between BMI and Serum HDL Cholesterol in type-2 Diabetic patients

Figure 3: Scatter diagram showing positive Correlation between BMI and Serum LDL Cholesterol in type-2 Diabetic patients

Discussion

The present study was conducted to find out the association between Body mass Index and Serum Total cholesterol, Serum HDL cholesterol and LDL cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients. The results of our study clearly indicate that, majority of the type-2 Diabetic patients were over-weight. A study done by Freemantle has shown that, there was a very strong association between obesity and development of type-2 Diabetes [7]. Obesity in type-2 Diabetes is strongly associated with development of Insulin resistance [8]. Adipocytes in the abdominal fat release free fatty acids into the circulation by lipolysis. This inturn impairs glucose uptake in skeletal muscles.

In a study done by Shah, it was observed that, most of the type-2 Diabetic patients were over-weight, and it was concluded that BMI and waist circumference were independent risk factors for the development of type-2 Diabetes [9]. Obesity is often associated with decreased production of adiponectin and Insulin -sensitizing peptide, which contributes to development of Insulin resistance [10]. Adiponectin has a major role in increasing fatty acid oxidation in muscle, thus decreasing serum triglyceride and free fatty acid levels. Type-2 Diabetic patients have reduced levels of circulating adiponectin, which inturn indicate that, adiponectin plays a major role in development of lipid abnormalities in type-2 Diabetes Mellitus [11].

In our study, we have demonstrated a statistically significant difference with ($p < 0.001$) in serum

Total Cholesterol levels and with ($p < 0.05$) in serum HDL Cholesterol levels, and with no statistical significance in serum LDL Cholesterol levels with increasing BMI in type-2 Diabetic patients. The findings in our study were in accordance with another study done by Hardev Singh Sandhu [12], which also showed statistically significant difference in serum Total Cholesterol, serum HDL Cholesterol and serum Triglyceride levels ($p < 0.001$) with increasing BMI values in type-2 Diabetic patients. In our study, the levels of serum Total Cholesterol and serum LDL Cholesterol, when correlated with BMI in type-2 Diabetic patients, showed a statistically significant positive correlation, with ($r = 0.40$) and ($r = 0.17$) respectively. The results of our study were found to be similar to another study done by Purna Bansal [13], which showed a positive correlation between BMI and LDL Cholesterol levels, and negative correlation between BMI and HDL Cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients.

Also, in our study, we have found a statistically significant negative correlation between BMI and HDL Cholesterol levels with ($r = -0.19$) in type-2 Diabetic patients. This finding was in accordance with a study done by Belete Biadgo [14], which showed significant negative correlation between BMI and HDL Cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients. Risk of cardiovascular complications and dyslipidemia increases significantly with increasing levels of BMI in Diabetes. The current public health guidelines recommend lifestyle changes along with diet

modifications in type-2 Diabetic patients, in order to attain normal BMI. In type-2 Diabetic patients with central obesity, there is increased lipolysis, which causes the liver to release more glucose and LDL cholesterol into the circulation.

There is also less glucose uptake by the muscles with Insulin resistance. This leads to progressive increase in blood glucose and triglycerides, with decrease in HDL Cholesterol and increase in LDL Cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients [15]. Because of the increasing cardiovascular risk, along with hyperglycemia and dyslipidemia in Diabetes, attaining normal BMI in type-2 Diabetic patients is very much essential.

Conclusion

Obesity is a major risk factor in type-2 Diabetes Mellitus, and dyslipidemia is more prevalent in type-2 Diabetic patients. There is a significant association between BMI and serum Total cholesterol, serum LDL cholesterol and serum HDL cholesterol levels in type-2 Diabetic patients. Hence, we strongly recommend regular follow up and periodic medical checkup with appropriate glycemic control and life style changes, in order to achieve weight loss goals, so as to control dyslipidemia and cardiovascular risk in type-2 Diabetes Mellitus.

Acknowledgements: All the authors of this study are sincerely thankful to all the study participants, who actively participated in this study.

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